

DataCite & INSPIRE: facilitating data preservation and reuse in High-Energy Physics

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for the INSPIRE collaboration

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DataCite Summer Meeting @Nordbib
Copenhagen, June 14th 2012

Outline

CERN and High-Energy Physics

Research data in HEP

Preservation | Access | Reuse

Barriers

Trusted workflows: DataCite & INSPIRE

Large Hadron Collider @ CERN

Large Hadron Collider @ CERN

Experiments and Collaborations @ CERN

PROTON PHYSICS: STABLE BEAMS

Energy:

3500 GeV

I(B1):

5.50e+13

I(B2):

5.54e+13

FBCT Intensity and Beam Energy

Updated: 00:02:58

Instantaneous Luminosity

Updated: 00:02:54

Comments 22-04-2011 00:02:52 :

** Stable Beams **

World record for luminosity for
hadron machine

Automatic LUMI LEVELING in IP8

BIS status and SMP flags

B1

B2

Link Status of Beam Permits

true

true

Global Beam Permit

true

true

Setup Beam

false

false

Beam Presence

true

true

Moveable Devices Allowed In

true

true

Stable Beams

true

true

AFS: 50ns_480b+1small_424_12_468_36bpl15nj

PM Status B1

ENABLED

PM Status B2

ENABLED

15 petabytes

or

1.7 million dual-layer DVDs

A large stack of books, illustrating the volume of information. The books are of various colors and sizes, piled high. A semi-transparent white box is overlaid on the center of the image, containing text.

15 petabytes

or

1000 times the information
printed in books every year

Spectrum of Research Data in HEP

For details, see also <http://arxiv.org/abs/1205.4667>

Data and Computing Centre @ CERN

RG 26

RG 26

RG 18

ATLAS Collaboration @ CERN

Spectrum of Research Data in HEP

For details, see also <http://arxiv.org/abs/1205.4667>

Publications +

Spectrum of Research Data in HEP

For details, see also <http://arxiv.org/abs/1205.4667>

re-use

(open) access

preservation

What HEP researchers think...

At what level of detail should data be preserved ?
(top/blue: theorists, bottom/green: experimentalists)

But, what about current practices

SEARCH FOR

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SWI-Schweiz KAP 644738

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Charged particle transverse momentum spectra in pp collisions at $\sqrt{s} = 0.9$ and 7 TeV The CMS collaboration
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Charged particle multiplicities in pp interactions at $\sqrt{s} = 0.9$, 2.36, and 7 TeV The CMS collaboration
- Journal Article
CMS tracking performance results from early LHC operation The CMS Collaboration
- Journal Article
The Strong Interaction at the Collider and Cosmic-Rays Frontiers David d'Enterria

Related Books at Springer.com

An Invitation to Quantum Field Theory

Alvarez-Gaumé, Luis, Vázquez-Mozo, Miguel A.

PHYSICS AND ASTRONOMY

JOURNAL OF HIGH ENERGY PHYSICS
 Volume 2010, Number 2 (2010), 41, DOI: 10.1007/JHEP02(2010)041 [Open Access](#)

Transverse-momentum and pseudorapidity distributions of charged hadrons in pp collisions at $\sqrt{s} = 0.9$ and 2.36 TeV

CMS Collaboration, V. Khachatryan, A. M. Sirunyan, A. Tumasyan, W. Adam, T. Bergauer, M. Dragicevic, J. Erö, M. Friedl and R. Frühwirth, *et al.*

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[SUPPLEMENTALS \(1\)](#) [REFERENCES \(33\)](#) [CITED BY \(67\)](#) [EXPORT CITATION](#) [ABOUT](#)

Abstract

Measurements of inclusive charged-hadron transverse-momentum and pseudorapidity distributions are presented for proton-proton collisions at $\sqrt{s} = 0.9$ and 2.36 TeV. The data were collected with the CMS detector during the LHC commissioning in December 2009. For non-single-diffractive interactions, the average charged-hadron transverse momentum is measured to be 0.46 ± 0.01 (stat.) ± 0.01 (syst.) GeV/c at 0.9 TeV and 0.50 ± 0.01 (stat.) ± 0.01 (syst.) GeV/c at 2.36 TeV, for pseudorapidities between -2.4 and $+2.4$. At these energies, the measured pseudorapidity densities in the central region, $dN_{ch}/d\eta|_{|\eta| < 0.5}$, are $3:48 \pm 0:02$ (stat.) ± 0.13 (syst.) and $4:47 \pm 0:04$ (stat.) ± 0.16 (syst.), respectively. The results at 0.9 TeV are in agreement with previous measurements and confirm the expectation of near equal hadron production in $\overline{p}p$ and pp collisions. The results at 2.36 TeV represent the highest-energy measurements at a particle collider to date.

Keywords Hadron-Hadron Scattering

ArXiv ePrint: 1002.0621

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CERN

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Related Issue Journal

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Charged particle transverse momentum spectra in pp collisions at $\sqrt{s} = 0.9$ and 7 TeV The CMS collaboration
 - Journal Article
Charged particle multiplicities in pp interactions at $\sqrt{s} = 0.9$, 2.36, and 7 TeV The CMS collaboration
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CMS tracking performance results from early LHC operation The CMS Collaboration
 - Journal Article
The Strong Interaction at the Collider and Cosmic-Rays Frontiers David d'Enterria

PHYSICS AND ASTRONOMY

JOURNAL OF HIGH ENERGY PHYSICS

Volume 2010, Number 2 (2010), 41, DOI: 10.1007/JHEP02(2010)041

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Supplemental Materials

[Perfect Transcription](#)

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www.PerfectTranscription.com

Related Books at Springer.com

Symmetry and Group Theory in Particle Physics

Costa, Giovanni, Fogli, Gianluigi

Journal of High Energy Physics

© SISSA, Trieste, Italy 2010

10.1007/JHEP02(2010)041

Electronic supplementary material

Below is the link to the electronic supplementary material.

[\(TXT 10.0 KB\)](#)

Data Tables

Figure 5a for 900 GeV (data not included in the published figure)

Errors shown are systematic and statistical errors added linearly.

Eta = 0.1

pt	value	error
0.15	5.51	0.48
0.25	6.25	0.54
0.35	5.15	0.44
0.45	3.89	0.34
0.55	2.91	0.26
0.65	2.25	0.20
0.75	1.65	0.15
0.85	1.23	0.11
0.95	0.95	0.09
1.1	0.64	0.06
1.3	0.37	0.03
1.5	0.22	0.02
1.7	0.13	0.01
1.9	0.09	0.01

Eta = 0.3

pt	value	error
0.15	5.47	0.48
0.25	6.39	0.55
0.35	5.29	0.46
0.45	4.09	0.36
0.55	3.12	0.27
0.65	2.25	0.20
0.75	1.65	0.15

Looking for THE place to be:

Where should data be preserved ?
(top/blue: theorists, bottom/green: experimentalists)

Barriers

...moving beyond the technical aspects

Worries: getting credit

To what extent are you concerned about the following issues related to giving access to preserved data ?

a) Preserved data could be used without giving proper credit to the original authors
(top/blue: theorists, bottom/green: experimentalists)

Worries: getting credit

To what extent are you concerned about the following issues related to giving access to preserved data ?

a) Preserved data could be used without giving proper credit to the original authors

Worries: inflation/noise

To what extent are you concerned about the following issues related to giving access to preserved data ?

b) Uncontrolled access to data may lead to an inflation of incorrect results
(top/blue: theorists, bottom/green: experimentalists)

Worries: documentation

If you were to re-use preserved data, to what extent would you be concerned by the following scenarios ?

d) I am not using the data correctly
(top/blue: theorists, bottom/green: experimentalists)

Reputation

Strategic approaches needed: one example from HEP

Study Group for Data Preservation and
Long Term Analysis in High Energy Physics

DPHEP-2012-001
May 2012

Status Report of the DPHEP Study Group: Towards a Global Effort for Sustainable Data Preservation in High Energy Physics

<http://arxiv.org/abs/1205.4667>

Also needed:

Trusted workflows - DataCite and INSPIRE

Data generation

Data processing

Data submission

Data record

Data DOI

Data reuse

Data citation

HEP Search

High-Energy Physics Literature Database

Use "find " for SPIRES-style search ([other tips](#))

[find j "Phys.Rev.Lett.,105"](#) :: [more](#)

HOW TO SEARCH

SPIRES syntax is (mostly) supported (requires "find")

[find a richter, b and t quark and date > 1984](#)

[find j phys.rev.,D50,1140 or j hep,0903,112](#)

[find eprint arxiv:1007.5048](#) (Note the plots available on the detailed record)

[find fulltext "quark-gluon plasma"](#) (Note new "fulltext" operator)

[find a ellis and refersto a witten](#) (Note "refersto")

[find a kane and citedby title SUSY and topcite 200+](#) (Note "citedby")

New techniques:

[1985 richter quark multiplicity](#)

[arXiv:1007.5048](#)

[citedby:author:ellis -refersto:author:witten](#)

[author:randall | author:sundrum cited:450->1350](#)

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[More search tips](#) and [full help](#)

INSPIRE UPDATES

See our blog at blog.inspirehep.net for updates on new features and other news. You can also follow us on [twitter](#). To send us feedback use feedback@inspirehep.net. The data in INSPIRE is derived from SPIRES, or better. To correct data in INSPIRE (or SPIRES)

50'000 users

1 Million records

500k full text

2 searches/second

50years hand curated
metadata

The Durham HepData Project

REACTION DATABASE

DATA REVIEWS

PARTON DISTRIBUTION FUNCTION SERVER

OTHER HEP

Reaction Database Standard Search Interface

Database of Numerical HEP scattering cross sections

Enter query:

Search

examples: re gamma gamma, re p p --> p p and obs sig, exp cern

[Search Help](#) [Output Help](#) [Form Search](#) [Browse Keywords](#) **Latest LHC DATA**

To search the database: Enter your query command comprising keyword-value pairs joined with Boolean ANDs. A null entry will retrieve all records.

The basic keywords are:

reac - the reaction (eg. p p --> charged x) also **beam** and **fsp**

obs - the observable (eg. SIG, DSIG/DX, DN/DPT)

sqrts - lower bound of the centre-of-mass energy in GeV

exp - the experiment/laboratory name (eg. ZEUS, CERN, LHC)

date - the year of the publication/preprint

auth - the first author name on the paper

ref - the publication/preprint reference **Use % as the right or left truncation character to search for values beginning or ending with the value. All searches are case-insensitive. More details are in the [Search Help](#).**

Information

References (55)

Citations (0)

Files

Plots

HEP Data

/ Experiment-HEP

arXiv:1109.6572

Search for squarks and gluinos using final states with jets and missing transverse momentum with the ATLAS detector in $\sqrt{s} = 7$ TeV proton-proton collisions

[Search for squarks and gluinos using final states with jets and missing transverse momentum with the ATLAS detector in \$\sqrt{s} = 7\$ TeV proton-proton collisions](#) - [Aad, Georges](#) *et al*

doi:10.7483/inspire-hep.data.123-456

Extra resource relating to the paper arxiv:1109.6572

Experimental acceptance/efficiency and excluded cross section*branching ratios:

[Signal expectations and experimental acceptance/efficiency for \$M_{\text{gluino}}\$ vs \$M_{\text{squark}}\$ grid \(massless LSP\)](#) , doi:10.7483/inspire-hep.data.Z12-345

[Signal expectations and experimental acceptance/efficiency for CMSSM/MSUGRA grid](#) , doi:10.7483/inspire-hep.data.543-21X

SLHA files:

[susy sqgl slha files](#), doi:10.7483/inspire-hep.data.432-1MN

[susy CMSSM/MSUGRA slha files](#) , doi:10.7483/inspire-hep.data.432-1BA

http://hepdata.cedar.ac.uk/resource/9212183/sqglx00_0IEPS_HEPdata.txt

mgl	msq	Expected # signal events (A,B,C,D,E)	Acceptance * efficiency (A,B,C,D,E)	Excluded (A,B)
200	200	0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00	0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00	0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00
200	300	0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00	0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00	0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00
200	400	0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00	0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00	0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00
200	500	1.13e+02,2.24e+02,1.79e+04,4.99e+02,1.74e+02	1.54e-04,3.05e-04,2.44e-02,6.80e-04,2.37e-04	1.54e-04,3.05e-04,2.44e-02,6.80e-04,2.37e-04
200	600	0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00	0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00	0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00
200	700	1.17e+02,1.17e+02,1.24e+04,0.00e+00,1.17e+02	1.75e-04,1.75e-04,1.86e-02,0.00e+00,1.75e-04	1.75e-04,1.75e-04,1.86e-02,0.00e+00,1.75e-04
200	800	0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00	0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00	0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00
200	900	0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00	0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00	0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00
200	1000	0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00	0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00	0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00
200	1200	0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00	0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00	0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00
200	1400	0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00	0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00	0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00
200	1600	0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00	0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00	0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00
200	1800	0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00	0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00	0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00
200	2000	0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00	0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00	0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00,0.00e+00
300	200	1.86e+02,5.52e+02,2.61e+04,4.86e+02,2.55e+02	2.91e-04,8.62e-04,4.08e-02,7.59e-04,3.98e-04	2.91e-04,8.62e-04,4.08e-02,7.59e-04,3.98e-04
300	300	3.33e+02,8.17e+02,1.90e+04,8.42e+02,2.79e+02	1.39e-03,3.40e-03,7.91e-02,3.50e-03,1.16e-03	1.39e-03,3.40e-03,7.91e-02,3.50e-03,1.16e-03
300	400	1.94e+02,4.61e+02,1.71e+04,5.32e+02,7.11e+02	1.40e-03,3.32e-03,1.23e-01,3.83e-03,5.12e-03	1.40e-03,3.32e-03,1.23e-01,3.83e-03,5.12e-03
300	500	2.17e+02,7.46e+02,1.29e+04,7.24e+02,8.64e+02	2.19e-03,7.52e-03,1.30e-01,7.30e-03,8.71e-03	2.19e-03,7.52e-03,1.30e-01,7.30e-03,8.71e-03
300	600	1.51e+02,4.79e+02,9.28e+03,4.95e+02,5.47e+02	1.85e-03,5.87e-03,1.14e-01,6.07e-03,6.71e-03	1.85e-03,5.87e-03,1.14e-01,6.07e-03,6.71e-03
300	700	6.47e+01,2.17e+02,7.94e+03,2.41e+02,4.01e+02	8.87e-04,2.98e-03,1.09e-01,3.30e-03,5.50e-03	8.87e-04,2.98e-03,1.09e-01,3.30e-03,5.50e-03
300	800	1.18e+02,3.86e+02,6.73e+03,4.87e+02,5.64e+02	1.72e-03,5.62e-03,9.81e-02,7.10e-03,8.22e-03	1.72e-03,5.62e-03,9.81e-02,7.10e-03,8.22e-03
300	900	1.69e+02,3.61e+02,6.44e+03,3.85e+02,3.34e+02	2.55e-03,5.46e-03,9.73e-02,5.82e-03,5.05e-03	2.55e-03,5.46e-03,9.73e-02,5.82e-03,5.05e-03
300	1000	5.58e+01,1.93e+02,6.47e+03,3.11e+02,2.71e+02	8.60e-04,2.98e-03,9.97e-02,4.79e-03,4.18e-03	8.60e-04,2.98e-03,9.97e-02,4.79e-03,4.18e-03
300	1200	4.28e+01,1.31e+02,6.16e+03,1.32e+02,1.45e+02	6.71e-04,2.05e-03,9.66e-02,2.07e-03,2.27e-03	6.71e-04,2.05e-03,9.66e-02,2.07e-03,2.27e-03
300	1400	1.05e+01,1.61e+02,5.54e+03,1.15e+02,1.27e+02	1.65e-04,2.53e-03,8.72e-02,1.81e-03,2.00e-03	1.65e-04,2.53e-03,8.72e-02,1.81e-03,2.00e-03
300	1600	2.04e+00,4.44e+01,6.25e+03,5.88e+01,2.03e+01	3.21e-05,6.99e-04,9.84e-02,9.25e-04,3.20e-04	3.21e-05,6.99e-04,9.84e-02,9.25e-04,3.20e-04
300	1800	3.20e+01,3.28e+01,5.71e+03,6.31e+01,2.67e+01	5.03e-04,5.15e-04,8.97e-02,9.91e-04,4.19e-04	5.03e-04,5.15e-04,8.97e-02,9.91e-04,4.19e-04
300	2000	3.28e+01,1.14e+02,5.81e+03,8.09e+01,1.70e+02	5.14e-04,1.79e-03,9.11e-02,1.27e-03,2.67e-03	5.14e-04,1.79e-03,9.11e-02,1.27e-03,2.67e-03
400	200	6.69e+02,8.48e+02,1.68e+04,1.27e+03,6.12e+01	1.83e-03,2.32e-03,4.60e-02,3.48e-03,1.68e-04	1.83e-03,2.32e-03,4.60e-02,3.48e-03,1.68e-04

Information

References (55)

Citations(9)

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HEP Data

[Search for squarks and gluinos using final states with jets and missing transverse momentum with the ATLAS detector in \$\sqrt{s} = 7\$ TeV proton-proton collisions](#) - [Aad, Georges](#) *et al*

Paper (arXiv:1109.6572) **cited by: 7 records**

[more](#)

Datasets (doi:10.7483/inspire-hep.data.123-456) **cited by: 2 records**

[more](#)

Trusted workflows: DataCite and INSPIRE

Data generation

Data processing

Data submission (e.g. via HEPData)

Data record

Data DOI

Data reuse

Data citation

Facilitating preservation and reuse in HEP via DataCite and INSPIRE

- Individual record for data
- DOIs for individual datasets and for collections
- Versioning
- Reuse tracking
- Collaboration with community platforms

More details...

Parse.Insight results: <http://www.parse-insight.eu/> and [arXiv:0906.0485v1](https://arxiv.org/abs/0906.0485v1)

DPHEP: www.dphep.org and [arXiv:1205.4667v1](https://arxiv.org/abs/1205.4667v1)

INSPIRE: www.inspirehep.net

Or drop us an email:

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feedback@inspirehep.net